

A Reproducibility Analysis on: Do Channels Matter? Illuminating Interpersonal Influence on Music Recommendations

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Abstract

Kim et al. [5] analyze the differences of music recommendations through the personal (e.g. friends or family) and non-personal (e.g. automatic recommendation system) channel and how they affect the adoption rate of music. Our work assesses the paper regarding reproducibility and generalizability of its results by using the same methods and differing mainly in the sampled population. We discovered that our observations differ considerably from the observations in the paper. Only a small number of observations are similar. Based on our sample size (about 30 persons from the European area) we conclude that the methods of the paper are reproducible but the results are not.

Keywords: Music Recommendation, Reproducibility, Survey Analysis, Statistics

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1 Introduction

Non-personal (e.g., from systems) or personal (e.g., from friends) music recommendations are key components in exploring new music. Based on the number of publications cited in the work of Kim et al. [5], we can observe, that the focus of research is more on the music recommendation of systems. Accordingly, there are hardly any publications that focus on the interpersonal channel and compare it with the non-personal recommendation in detail. However, there is still sufficient evidence that interpersonal recommendations are important components in discovering new music. Therefore, Kim et al. conduct in their work titled “Do Channels Matter? Illuminating Interpersonal Influence on Music Recommendations” [5] a survey-based study to acquire more knowledge about the differences of personal and non-personal music recommendations. They analyze data by using 2-tailed paired t-tests, principal component analysis, linear and multivariate regression and visualize significant parameters.

However, Kim et al. [5] conducted the survey solely in Korea, so the results might be biased towards the Korean culture. Hence, there is no evidence that the results are generalizable and apply to other countries or different ethnic groups. To be able to generalize the findings, researchers would need to collect data uniformly around the world. This involves a huge amount of work, as the surveys would have to be in different languages, many people would have to be motivated to complete the survey and additional analysis would have to be done to draw correct conclusions (for example, recommendation systems could vary in effectiveness depending on the country and skew the survey results accordingly). The work of Kim et al. [5] state the ambition to repeat the analysis among multiple cultures in their future work section. However, since the work was only published in late 2020, presenting those results may take some time. Therefore, our work reproduces the work of Kim et al. with a different data set (mainly European participants) to make assumptions about the generalizability of their results.

2 Methodology

The reproducibility analysis aims to generalize the paper results by executing the same analyzes on a different set of raw data. Referring to the *PRIMAD*-Model [2], we stay as close as possible to the original experiment setup by using the same parameters, platform *R*, packages [3, 4, 6] and methods. Nevertheless, Kim et al. [5] do not provide the original data or code, which leads to changes in the implementation, as well as in the input data. The gain we aim to reach through this analysis is to generalize the applicability across different settings, as well as evaluating the correctness of the implementation and reviewing the flexibility and adoption. Also, we recreated the same survey and used the same statistical methods, since both were described in detail. Finally, both our paper and the original paper aim to compare personal and non-personal music recommendations, which yields the same research objective. Accordingly, we established a valid scientific basis to conclude the reproducibility.

2.1 Data Gathering

The survey was designed using a web-based survey software called *SurveyMonkey* [1]. This open-source voice of customer tool is the global leader in survey software and provides efficient support during the design and distribution of the survey. The duplicated survey was distributed with a web link and answered by a total of 32 users. The participants were mainly students living in different European countries. After pre-processing the responses, a total of 27 qualified as usable for the analysis, as some participants did not answer a sufficient amount of questions to be considered a valid instance.

2.2 Survey Analysis

To analyze the survey, we first had to remove personal information automatically gathered by SurveyMonkey, like IP-addresses. For the calculation of means and standard deviations, the participants who didn't fill out the whole survey were excluded. Table 1 shows the results of this calculation. A two-tailed paired t-test was conducted to capture the significance of each feature. Relevance, Diversity, Novelty and Serendipity had p-values of 0.1733, 0.1306, 0.3343, 0.486 respectively and therefore showed no statistically significant differences between the two channels. Figure 1 displays these results.

Figure 1. Evaluation criteria

Only Frequency showed a significant difference with p-value = 0.005402 and was therefore rated significantly higher for non-interpersonal channels.

Figure 2. Frequency

Convenience yields a p-value of 1 and thus had the same mean under the consideration that for the paired t-test only participants were included, which filled out the survey, both for the interpersonal and the non-interpersonal channel.

Figure 3. Convenience

The p-value of the Adoption rate is 0.6392 according to a paired t-test with a mean difference of 2.9, although the plot of the adoption rates shows a much higher mean for the interpersonal channel. This is due to people who are not receiving music recommendations through an automated channel rating the adoption rate through the interpersonal channel significantly higher than people who receive recommendations through both channels. Conducting simply a two-tailed t-test and including both groups, the p-value

	Interpersonal ($N = 26$)		Non-Interpersonal ($N = 16$)	
	Mean	Std.	Mean	Std.
Relevance	3.538	0.71	3.625	1.02
Diversity	3.615	0.7	3.0	1.15
Novelty	3.385	0.98	3.813	0.75
Serendipity	3.461	0.86	3.188	0.98
Frequency	2.885	0.65	3.75	0.86
Convenience	3.423	0.86	3.563	0.96
Adoption rate	44.46	22.04	33.56	23.41

Table 1. Summary of our survey result showing means and standard deviation (in brackets) for relevance, diversity, novelty, serendipity, and convenience from a 5-point *Likert*-scale (1 - “strongly disagree”, 5 - “strongly agree”), and percentages for adoptionrate. Bolded numbers are the higher mean values between interpersonal and non-interpersonal and provide a fast visual comparison.

shrinks to 0.1444. That means while this result resembles more the distribution in Figure 4 the difference still doesn't rise to significance

Figure 4. Adoption Rate

The principal component analysis (PCA) showed that the first two principal components accounted for 55% of the total variance. Relevance hardly contributes to PC1 or PC2. Serendipity and Diversity make up most of the variance of PC1, while Novelty contributes most of the variance for PC2. This indicates that Diversity and Serendipity are closely correlated, while Novelty seems to have little to no correlation at all to these two.

Finally, we characterized the relationship between Adoption rate and Frequency by applying linear regression. Firstly, we tried to predict the Adoption rate considering only Frequency as an input variable which didn't show any reasonable results with an F-statistic of 0.02724, a p-value of 0.8702 for interpersonal channels. The non-interpersonal channel had an F-statistic of 0.7371 and a p-value of 0.405, therefore Frequency alone isn't a reasonable feature to predict adoption rate. We also conducted multivariate regression considering all features as independent variables. The whole model using all features yields a F-statistic of 2.5 and a p-value of 0.055 and is therefore very close to being significant. Calculating another model using just Novelty as a predictive feature results in an F-statistic of 7.761 with a p-value of 0.009833 which lets us assume significance for this model. For the non-interpersonal channel no features were significant (F-statistic: 0.9435, p-value: 0.5099).

Figure 5. PCA visualization of the first two principal components

2.3 Limitation and Critical Reflection

Different from the original paper by Kim et al. [5] it was not possible to collect any personal information about the survey participants. Due to the General Data Protection Regulation, the distribution of attributes like age, gender or nationality among the participants is unknown. Moreover, the full sample size of 32 is still not enough to present significant results. Hence, the results might not represent the overall population and do not serve for statistical inference.

3 Reproducibility Analysis

Our fundamental assumption is that the paper should be reproducible. Thus, in the following section, we will focus exclusively on the differences between the results of the paper and ours to determine whether it can be reproduced with different input data and code as well. For comparing the means, we again applied a t-test to check if the difference is significant or not. As we do not have the original data we created artificial samples with the same sample size N the same mean and the same standard deviation as shown in Table 3 of the original paper. These artificial samples are then compared to our results by conducting two-tailed t-tests.

Mean and Standard-deviation: Our statistical testing showed that Frequency and Convenience are significantly different for the interpersonal channel. For the non-interpersonal channel, only Frequency has a significant difference. Thus, in both channels, the sample population receives music significantly more frequent than the sample population in the original paper. Also, it is significantly more convenient to get new music from the interpersonal channel for our sample population.

Usage behaviour: Kim et al. [5] states that “Non-interpersonal channels surpassed interpersonal channels in terms of its usage behaviour – frequency, convenience, and adoption rate” (Chapter 4, Kim et. al [5]). In our analysis, this holds only for Frequency. As mentioned already, Convenience has no significant difference and Adoption rate is higher in the interpersonal channel. We can therefore not confirm, that the non-interpersonal channel surpassed the interpersonal channel.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA): The visualization of the PCA-results in the work of Kim et al. [5] shows, that Diversity, Novelty, Serendipity correlate to each other, while Relevance points to the orthogonal direction and thus, doesn’t correlate with another attribute. Diversity and Serendipity also correlate to each other, while Novelty doesn’t correlate to other attributes.

Linear Regression: Kim et al. [5] found a relationship between Frequency and Adoption rate using linear regression, by showing that Frequency has a significant effect on Adoption rate in both channels (interpersonal: $[F(1,153)=6.324, p<0.05]$; Non-interpersonal: $[F(1,141)=5.09, p<0.05]$). However, we could not observe this relationship. Instead, what we found was that for the interpersonal channel, Novelty seemed to be a reasonable predictive feature which wasn’t reported in the paper.

Multivariate Regression: Lastly, we conducted a multivariate regression to analyze the effect on Adoption Rate for both channels. In this context, Kim et al. [5] state “Relevance ($p<0.001$) and novelty ($p<0.05$) showed significant effects in interpersonal channels while relevance ($p<0.001$) and diversity ($p<0.05$) were found to have significant effect in adoption of recommendations from non-interpersonal channels” (Chapter 4, Kim et. al [5]). While the original paper names Relevance and Novelty as attributes with significant effects in interpersonal channels, our observation only proved Novelty was significant for the interpersonal channel. For the non-interpersonal channel, the original paper names Relevance and Diversity as attributes with a significant effect on the Adoption rate. However, we observed that no attribute is significant in the non-interpersonal channel. In summary, only Novelty was the attribute for which we could measure a similar effect on the interpersonal channel. All other results differ from our observations.

4 Conclusion

In this work, we investigated the paper by Kim et al. [5] for reproducibility. The methods of the work are described in detail, such that the workflow could be reproduced exactly. However, we observed that only a few of their results are consistent with ours (see Chapter 3). According to the *PRI-MAD*-model [2], this difference can be attributed to either the data (e.g. sample too small, different culture), different implementations (different methods or parameters within the packages), or biased research. We strongly suspect that the differences in data are the cause of differing results. For example, culture, or more specifically the way people listen to music, can cause channels to be used differently. Additionally, the systems used may differ (e.g. *Spotify*, *Apple Music* for our sample vs. applications from Korea), so that the recommendations through a system may be of different quality. Kim et al. [5] also suspect that the results may be strongly dependent on culture, so they plan to collect cross-cultural data in the future. Since, we can neither confirm nor completely reject the hypothesis of the paper based on our sample, the plan of analyzing more transnational data is necessary to draw more general statements.

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